

CHARACTERISATION OF ELASTIC PROPERTIES OF LAMINATED COMPOSITES BY NON-DESTRUCTIVE TECHNIQUES

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SUMMARY

Dynamic and static methods for a non-destructive characterization of the elastic properties of advanced composites are examined in the present paper. A comparative study is done to find out a preferable approach for the characterization of laminated composites depending on laboratory facilities.

Keywords: laminated composites, elastic properties, non-destructive techniques, static test, vibration test, inverse problem.

1. INTRODUCTION

Composites, like investigated in the present study, are seen as an area of high growth in the world, due to their intrinsic benefits and crucial role in different industrial sectors such as aerospace, land transport, marine and construction. Unfortunately the material data provided by manufacturers very often do not contain all necessary information to predict the behaviour of advanced composite structures using different analysis tools. Additionally, due to relative high costs of composites, their experimental testing using conventional fracture methods suffer from high expenses too. On that reason, the development of non-destructive dynamic and static techniques for characterisation of elastic properties of advanced composite materials is required.

One of the first attempts for obtaining elastic properties of structure based on non-destructive vibration test appears in [1], where the Timoshenko beam theory is used to establish equations for computing the elastic and shear modulus from the fundamental flexural and torsional frequencies of prisms and cylinders. This approach has been extended in [2] with a refinement in experimental techniques as well as in the theoretical calculating for elastic modulus from the appropriate fundamental frequencies. The work done in [1-2] has formed the base of the ASTM standard test method [3] for characterisation of dynamic elastic properties based on impulse excitation.

Due to the development of numerical methods for structural analysis as well as laboratory instrumentation for dynamic testing, the vibration test methods have been refined by the mixed numerical-experimental (inverse) techniques. All the inverse methods have been appreciated at once because of their non-destructive nature and practical application for the characterisation of isotropic and orthotropic materials

behaviour [4-7]. The inverse techniques are based on the minimisation of an error functional which describes the discrepancy between experimentally measured and numerically calculated eigenfrequencies of structures. By minimising the functional the identification parameters i.e., elastic properties, are obtained.

In contrast to the vibration based methods and inverse techniques, the conventional static methods for determining elastic parameters of composite materials are based on a direct measurement of strain fields [8]. Boundary effect, sample preparation and difficulties in obtaining homogeneous stress and strain fields are serious problems. As a result an indirect methods based on static approach have received most attention. For instance, a measurement of three strains in the axial, lateral, and diagonal directions of a composite beam utilizing three-point-bending test has been used in [9] for the elastic constants identification.

In the present investigation an attempt is made to find out the preferable approach for the non-destructive characterization of laminated composites depending on laboratory facilities. On that reason, a static approach using three-point-bending test, and two dynamic methods, namely, impulse excitation method and an inverse procedure based on the planning of experiments and response surface methodology, are applied for determination of elastic properties of laminated composite plates.

2. NUMERICAL AND EXPERIMENTAL ANALYSES

Two carbon fibre XP45 Turane Resin laminated composite plates and four beams cut from the plates along their principal directions 1, 2 (two beams from each plate), are chosen for the present study. The geometry, stacking sequence, and density of each test specimen are given in Table 1.

2.1. Numerical model

In the present investigation the finite element method is used to analyse the dynamic response of plates with free-free boundary conditions in ANSYS, where the laminated composite plates are modelled by the linear layered structural shell elements SHELL99. The modal analysis with block Lanczos mode-extraction method is applied to determine eigenfrequencies and eigenmodes.

2.2. Experimental set-up of dynamic tests

For the experimental dynamic tests the POLYTEC Scanning Laser Vibrometer PSV-400-B is used for non-contact vibration sensing (Figure 1). It consists of the optical

Table 1. Geometry, stacking sequence, and density of specimens.

Specimen	Stacking sequence	Length (m)	Width (m)	Thickness (m)	Density (kg/m ³)
Plate 1	[0/90/0/90] _s	0.300	0.200	0.00024	1478.80
Plate 2	[0/90/45/-45] _s	0.300	0.200	0.00024	1364.90
Beam 1 ¹	[0/90/0/90] _s	0.300	0.015	0.00024	1478.80
Beam 2 ¹	[0/90/0/90] _s	0.200	0.015	0.00024	1478.80
Beam 3 ²	[0/90/45/-45] _s	0.300	0.015	0.00024	1364.40
Beam 4 ²	[0/90/45/-45] _s	0.200	0.015	0.00024	1364.40

¹ cut from Plate 1 along principal directions 1,2; ² cut from Plate 2 along principal directions 1,2

Figure 1. PSV-400-B experimental set-up.

Figure 2. Three-point-bending test.

scanning head PSV-I-400 LR equipped with a high sensitive vibrometer sensor OFV-505, controller OFV-5000, junction box PSV-E-400, power amplifier Bruel&Kjaer 2732, computer system with a data acquisition board and PSV software 8.6. A specimen is excited with the periodic chirp signal generated by the internal generator using the loudspeaker (SP-106WP) providing non-contact excitation. As a result, the specimen starts to vibrate within the frequency band of the input signal. The vibrometer controller automatically moves the measurement beam to the each point of the defined scanning grid sensing its back-scattered light. The photo-detector, operating on Doppler frequency shift between measurement and reference beams, measures the time depended vibration velocity and validates measurements with the signal-to-noise ratio. After the measurements have been performed at the each point, the averaged time response is transformed to the frequency domain using Fast Fourier Transform giving as a result - frequency response function used for estimation of structural natural frequencies and corresponding mode shapes.

2.3. Experimental set-up of the static test

The Zwick Z-100 system is used for the realization of the three-point-bending test. The system allows applying quasi-static loading for determination of elastic properties of a beam specimen [10] (Figure 2). The 10 kN load cell is used for the bending load. A beam specimen rests on two supports and is loaded by means of a loading nose in the middle span between them. It is centred on the supports, with its long axis perpendicular to the loading nose and supports. The loading speed of 0.01 mm/s is set for all tests and the load-deflection data are preserved by measurement of the motion of the loading nose relative to the supports.

3. NON-DESTRUCTIVE METHODS

The plates considered in the present study are assumed to be thin and orthotropic in a state of plane stress. In this case, four independent engineering constants of the laminated plates are sought, namely, Young's moduli E_1 and E_2 in plate principal directions, in-plane shear modulus G_{12} , and Poisson's ratio ν_{12} .

In the current study the engineering constants of laminated composites plates are determined by three non-destructive techniques based on static and dynamic approaches, which are described in the following subsections.

3.1. Static test

A non-destructive static approach based on the three-point-bending test principle [10] is applied using beam like samples in order to determine their elastic properties (Figure 2). In this case, the deflection of a beam with a rectangular cross section is given as follows

$$\delta = \frac{PL^3}{4bh^3E} \quad (1)$$

where E is the longitudinal Young's modulus, P (N) is an applied load, L (m) is a span length, b (m) is a width of a beam, and h (m) is a thickness. By the use of Eq. (1), it is assumed that the dimensions of the beam are such that all the deflection is due to axial deformation only. Eq. (1) can be rearranged to the following form

$$\frac{\delta}{PL} = \frac{L^2}{4bh^3E} \quad (2)$$

Therefore a set of three-point-bending tests conducted at different values of span will generate a series of values of δ_i/PL_i , where i denotes the subsequent span lengths. A graph of δ_i/PL_i plot against L_i^2 should give a straight line which slope is equal to

$$g = \frac{1}{4bh^3E} \Rightarrow E = \frac{1}{4bh^3g} \quad (3)$$

from which Young's modulus is calculated.

In order to keep this approach non-destructive, it is important to ensure that the deflection δ can fully recover at the end of each bend test. On that reason this approach is only applicable for the elastic behaviour of composites which can be obtained usually for strains less than 0.5%.

Four beams listed in Table 1 have been tested experimentally as described in Section 2.3 in order to determine engineering constants of the laminated composites plates. For each beam five three-point-bending tests have been performed for the span lengths $L_i = 0.12, 0.10, 0.08, 0.06, 0.04$ m, respectively. The first test of each beam ($L_i = 0.12$ m) was terminated when the deflection reached the beam thickness ($\delta_1 = h$), what assure the strain less or equal 0.5%. Afterwards, the value of the applied load P for $\delta_1 = h$ has been used to terminate the subsequent four tests of each beam. For each span length L_i the load-deflection data (P and δ_i) have been preserved in order to calculate the values of δ_i/PL_i and plot them against L_i^2 . Obtained graphs have been approximated by the linear regression lines from which the slopes g have been determined (Figure 3). Using Eq. (3), the Young's moduli of each beam have been calculated and listed in Table 2.

3.2. Impulse excitation

Vibration test based on the impulse excitation is adopted for the determination of elastic properties of composites beams [3]. Beam like specimens used for this method

Table 2. Young's moduli obtained from three-point-bending test.

Specimen	Slope	E_1 (GPa)	E_2 (GPa)
Beam 1	0.01793	67.20	-
Beam 2	0.03215	-	37.50
Beam 3	0.02246	53.70	-
Beam 4	0.03457	-	34.90

Figure 3. Regression lines after the set of three-point-bending tests.

have specific resonant frequencies that are determined by the elastic modulus, material density, and geometry. Therefore the main requirement is to establish dimensions, density, and experimental fundamental flexural and torsional frequencies of a beam with free-free boundary conditions, so that the elastic properties can be computed. Using the fundamental flexural frequency the Young's modulus in the longitudinal direction of a beam can be calculated as follows [1-3]

$$E = 0.9465 \frac{\rho f_b^2 l^4}{h^2} T_1 \quad (4)$$

where ρ (kg/m^3) is a density, f_b (Hz) is the fundamental frequency in bending, h (m) is a thickness, l (m) is a length, and T_1 is the correction factor. The third resonant frequency

Figure 4. Example of experimentally obtained fundamental mode shapes of Beam 3:
a) in bending, b) in torsion.

of a beam is associated with fundamental torsional mode and can be used to calculate the in-plane shear modulus as follows

$$G = 4\rho f_t^2 l^2 R \quad (5)$$

where f_t (Hz) is the fundamental frequency in torsion and R is the correction factor.

In order to estimate the engineering constants of the plates, four beams listed in Table 1 have been tested experimentally to obtain their fundamental flexural and torsional frequencies. The frequencies have been determined using POLYTEC Laser Scanning Vibrometer PSV-400-B in the 0 ... 1600 Hz frequency bandwidth with excitation provided by loudspeaker. Free-free boundary conditions have been simulated by suspending beams on two thin threads at the locations of nodal lines of beam's bending mode ($0.224l$ from each end). One vibration test for each beam has been performed to determine its fundamental bending and torsional frequencies as well as corresponding mode shapes (Figure 4). The Eqs. (4-5) have been then used to calculate E_1 , E_2 , and G_{12} of the beams. The fundamental frequencies and calculated engineering constants are listed in Table 3.

Table 3. Young's and in-plane shear moduli obtained from impulse excitation.

Specimen	f_b (Hz)	f_t (Hz)	E_1 (GPa)	E_2 (GPa)	G_{12} (GPa)
Beam 1 ¹	183.50	899.50	66.25		4.80
Beam 2 ²	304.00	1335.50	-	35.90	4.77
Beam 3 ¹	170.25	1025.00	52.60	-	5.76
Beam 4 ²	308.25	1530.00	-	34.10	5.78

¹ $T_1 = 1.00042$ and $R = 11.15$; ² $T_1 = 1.00095$ and $R = 11.30$ [3]

Figure 5. Inverse technique procedure.

3.3. Inverse method

A proposed inverse technique [11] consists of six steps shown in Figure 5. In the first step the plan of experiment is developed in dependence on the number of unknown parameters n and number of experiments k . To assure the regular distribution of the points of the experiment in the domain of parameters, the following criterion is used

$$\phi = \sum_{i=1}^k \sum_{j=i+1}^k \frac{1}{l_{ij}^2} \Rightarrow \min \quad (6)$$

where l_{ij} is the distance between the point having numbers i and j ($i \neq j$). In the second step FE analysis is performed in the reference points of the experimental design and dynamic parameters of structure are calculated. In the third step the numerical data obtained by FEM are used to determine a simple function using the response surface approach. Simultaneously the physical vibration test is performed and dynamic parameters, namely, natural frequencies and corresponding mode shapes, of a real structure are preserved. In the fifth step the error functional between the experimentally measured and numerically calculated eigenfrequencies of a structure is written as

$$\Phi(\mathbf{x}) = \sum_{i=1}^I w_i \frac{(f_i^{EXP} - f_i^{FEM}(\mathbf{x}))^2}{(f_i^{EXP})^2} \Rightarrow \min \quad (7)$$

where w_i are the weights for the identification functional, I is the number of resonant frequencies, f_i^{EXP} are the experimentally measured natural frequencies, and $f_i^{FEM}(\mathbf{x})$ are eigenfrequencies obtained from the response surface approximation representing the relationship between the numerical eigenfrequencies and the vector (\mathbf{x}) of unknown parameters n . An identification of the unknown parameters is performed in the final step minimizing the error functional, Eq.(7), subjected to the bounds of identification parameters and conditions of a positive definiteness of the elasticity matrix.

The inverse technique has been utilized to identify four engineering constants of the two laminated composites plates. The experiment design with four unknown parameters

($n = 4$), namely, $E_1, E_2, G_{12}, \nu_{12}$, and 101 experiment points ($k = 101$) have been selected. The borders for unknown parameters are taken as follows

$$\begin{array}{ll}
 \text{Plate - 1} & \text{Plate - 2} \\
 60 \leq E_1 \leq 70 \text{GPa}, & 50 \leq E_1 \leq 60 \text{GPa}, \\
 30 \leq E_2 \leq 40 \text{GPa}, & 30 \leq E_2 \leq 40 \text{GPa}, \\
 5 \leq G_{12} \leq 7 \text{GPa}, & 5 \leq G_{12} \leq 7 \text{GPa}, \\
 0.25 \leq \nu_{12} \leq 0.30 & 0.25 \leq \nu_{12} \leq 0.35
 \end{array} \quad (8)$$

The FE model of the each plate has been built as described in Section 2.1, and modal analyses have been performed in 101 experiment points for the each plate. Ten first eigenfrequencies has been determined from each analysis and the numerical results have been employed to obtain approximating functions (response surface). The physical vibration test has been performed for two plates as described in Section 2.2 in the 0 ... 1600 Hz bandwidth. Free-free boundary condition have been simulated by suspending plates on two thin threads attached to the upper corners of the plates (Figure 1). Ten first natural frequencies have been determined for each plate. Minimizing the error functional, the engineering constants have been identified and listed in Table 4, together with results obtained in Section 3.1 and 3.2. For the results validation purpose, the experimentally measured natural frequencies of the two plates were compared with the numerically obtained eigenfrequencies, employing the identified engineering constants by inverse technique (Table 5).

3. CONCLUSIONS

In the present study non-destructive static and dynamic methods have been applied for the characterization of elastic properties of laminated composite plates. Depending on the method two, three or four engineering constants of the composite laminated plates have been determined.

The application of the three-point-bending test allowed determining only Young's moduli in the principal directions of the plates. Despite of this, the advantage of the method is its non-destructive nature under static load. Moreover, the fact that any strain gages have been attached to the beam samples allows using them for the further

Table 4. Identified engineering constants of laminated composites plates.

	Testing method		
	Three-point-bending	Impulse excitation	Inverse technique
	<u>Plate 1</u>		
E_1 (GPa)	67.20	66.25	65.97
E_2 (GPa)	37.50	35.90	36.80
G_{12} (GPa)	-	4.79	4.46
ν_{12}	-	-	0.28
	<u>Plate 2</u>		
E_1 (GPa)	53.70	52.60	51.70
E_2 (GPa)	34.90	34.10	33.00
G_{12} (GPa)	-	5.77	6.08
ν_{12}	-	-	0.315

Table 5. Experimental and numerical resonant frequency.

Mode (i)	Plate 1			Plate 2		
	FEM ¹ (Hz)	EXP (Hz)	$\Delta\%$	FEM ¹ (Hz)	EXP (Hz)	$\Delta\%$
1	71.70	71.50	0.28	89.26	89.75	0.55
2	175.90	176.00	0.06	134.97	133.75	0.91
3	229.70	231.00	0.56	227.59	227.75	0.07
4	301.30	301.00	0.10	365.58	363.75	0.50
5	329.44	328.00	0.44	388.18	394.25	1.54
6	463.46	459.25	0.92	438.47	434.75	0.86
7	494.12	490.00	0.84	464.04	458.75	1.15
8	533.88	541.00	1.32	555.59	550.25	0.97
9	740.86	735.25	0.76	745.34	753.75	1.12
10	822.36	827.25	0.59	789.36	794.25	0.67
Average			0.60	0.83		

¹FEM analysis for engineering constant obtained from the inverse technique

investigation. However, systematic errors arise in this approach, especially when the span length is measured. On that reason the tests should be performed for the possible high number of spans so that the correlation factor of the linear regression line approaches 100% and the slope is determined with small error.

A simple and effective method for engineering constants identification appears when the vibration method based on impulse excitation principle is applied. The Young's moduli in the principal directions as well as in-plane shear modulus of the plates have been estimated applying this method. The advantage of this method over the proposed static approach is little preparation of experimental set-up and only two vibration tests are required in order to estimate three engineering constants of the plate. The only limitation of this method is a need of advanced equipment for vibration data acquisition.

Among all proposed methods for the elastic properties characterization, the approach based on the inverse technique is most suited for the convenient, fast, and accurate identification of elastic properties. Four engineering constants of each laminated composite plate have been successfully determined. For that purpose, only one vibration test was needed to acquire resonant frequency of each plate. However, as it was a case in the impulse excitation method, the instrumentation used for the physical test should provide non-contact vibration sensing and excitation in order to reduce measurement error.

Although the static and impulse excitation methods do not provide information about all engineering constants, they can be used as a preliminary tests in order to assess the initial bounds of engineering constants for the identification procedure with application of the inverse technique.

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